

SOCIAL MEDIA PROPAGANDA AND PERCEPTION MANIPULATION THROUGH FIFTH-GENERATION WAR NARRATIVE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN ISLAMABAD

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Abstract:

This empirical research study is based on structured survey of 220 university students from ten public and private sector universities in Islamabad. Researcher examines how students perceive and respond to Inter-Services Public Relations (ISPR) messaging on fifth-generation war disseminated via social media platforms. This research study is drawing on Noam Chomsky's propaganda model. This research study thoroughly explores social media's role in state-led perception manipulation narrative. Findings of this study indicates that the moderate to high awareness and acceptance of the fifth-generation war narrative, with the statement "Social media is battlefield for hostile states" scoring the highest mean (4.02) and standard deviation is (0.78). ISPR exposure correlated with strong acceptance where the mean is (4.12) and the SD is (0.58). Using statistical analysis the Pearson correlation revealed a significant positive relationship between exposure and acceptance ($r = 0.62$, $p < 0.01$). This is moderated by critical media literacy (reduced to $r = 0.41$). Moreover, the study highlights the effectiveness of ISPR's social media strategies in shaping university students' perceptions. Social media role is also underscoring the mitigating role of media literacy in perception management.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Pakistan, the debate over fifth-generation war has gained particular urgency for policymakers and media analysts. It deals with the challenges modelled by rapid technological change and transnational information flows since the dawn of human history, war has undergone constant change. Unconventional war, hybrid war, information-based operations, media implantation, and fifth-generation war are examples of new fighting strategies and tactics that are emerging, weakening the effectiveness of traditional military techniques and obfuscating the distinction between battle and peace (Maisaia, 2024). The fifth-generation war is ambiguous and unclear rather than explicit.

Naturally, this leads to violence in state that either directly or indirectly affects public lives and property, infrastructure, state institutions, and financial resources like banks. Given the numerous continuous wars that exist today, including terrorism, ethnic and sectarian divide, media propaganda against state institutions, and money laundering, fifth-generation war poses an active threat to Pakistan's economy and internal and external security (Husain et al., 2022).

With the internet and social media playing crucial roles, combat in the twenty-first century has transformed into battle of "perception and information". This involves the dissemination of misinformation, propaganda, and fake news

using social media sites including Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and WhatsApp. The current study explores the relationship between digital media and fifth-generation war. Fifth-generation war is defined by its ambiguity and functions clandestinely through psychological disruption, information transmission, and narrative manipulation, often with no obvious or identifiable attacker (Treglia, 2010). This kind of non-kinetic war in the twenty-first century is referred to as "fifth-generation war," term that has expanded beyond traditional military war to encompass information, perception, and psychological effects on enemies. The battlefield is no longer the only place where wars take place. Social media, digital platforms, and other tools are being used more and more to fight them online. These instruments are intended to disrupt long-standing social systems and influence public opinion.

Social media is become the primary source of news and opinions for large number of Pakistanis. First and foremost, this has sociological implications for Pakistan's social cohesiveness and togetherness among its various ethnic groups, particularly among young people, who may be negatively impacted. The malicious propaganda of hostile powers is influencing disgruntled youth who lack direction and purpose, which could serve as catalyst for further separation and discord in Pakistan's already split society. Second, there is good chance that disgruntled youngsters may get disenchanted with the state apparatus, be swayed by hostile propaganda, and engage in anti-state activities. Pakistan is located in very significant geographical and strategic area of the world. It demonstrates its significance to the superpowers of the world. China, wealthy nation, is on the other side of India, longstanding adversary. Iran is a neighbour that is still at war with the United States.

The Inter-Services Public Relations (ISPR), the military's media and communication arm, played crucial role in protecting the concept of fifth-generation war (Nawaz et al, 2023). In what is known as the "*Bajwa Doctrine*", the nation's military chief, *Qamar Javed Bajwa*, outlined his strategy throughout his term from 2018 to 2021, making information and propaganda war key component of both domestic and national security. Consequently, the idea of fifth-

generation war emerged as defining feature of modern communication and war discourse in the country's online military's arsenal. It shifted traditional battlefield confrontations toward international wars based on information and perception manipulation. Ever since, the term Fifth-generation war represents national security framework that allows to exploit the digital sphere to shape and reshape public opinion in achieving national security goals. In other words, social media platforms have become pivotal arenas where state and non-state actors can disseminate (dis) information to influence their target audience, especially youth (Khan et al., 2024).

The study investigates how university students comprehend and react to the ISPR's social media messaging on fifth-generation war, conducting poll across ten Islamabad-based universities, the study asks: what is the statistical relationship between the level of students' exposure to ISPR's online content and their agreement with the state's narrative of fifth-generation war? Because university students are generally quite active on digital platforms and strategically important for influencing future political discourse.

It is imperative that their exposure to ISPR narratives and perspectives must be taken into consideration. At least, the ISPR's rhetoric of fifth generation war is targeted at them. By situating the analysis within the theoretical framework of Chomsky's propaganda model, the study contributes to the growing body of research on information war and university students' perception (Alam et al., 2024). It shows how war is conceptualised and communicated to make it palatable to the public in Pakistan. Apart from the Pakistan military's framing of security threats in terms of war narratives (Khan & Batool, 2025), the country's political elites also accuse the Taliban and Indian media of using social media to incite Pakistani youth against the military, the country's most powerful institution (Aziz et al., 2024). Social media's role has been extremely harmful since it has terrible impact on the brains of young, naive Pakistanis. We also discovered that most of our young people have access to social media apps and the internet. Young people are growing more dependent on the internet and feel helpless to resist their cravings. Propaganda and false information are being disseminated against Pakistan's state

machinery through social media. On Facebook and Twitter, fictitious accounts with different surnames were made with the intention of disseminating misleading information regarding crimes carried out by security forces.

Background

The term "*Bajwa Doctrine*" refers to the strategic vision of former Pakistani Army Chief Gen. *Qamar Javed Bajwa*, which was first presented in 2018. It focuses on regional peace, economic stability particularly China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), strengthening civil and military relations, and reaffirming Pakistan's position against United States pressure. It shifts from merely counter-terrorism to broader national security, encompassing economic diplomacy and more assertive international posture. However, opinions differ; some see it as bringing militants into politics or shift away from chauvinism. Earlier, former DG ISPR Maj Gen *Asif Ghafoor* made the first mention of the alleged doctrine latterly called "*Bajwa Doctrine*". This philosophy also provides guide for dealing with the nation's intricate and deeply embedded economic and governance problems. Several points are necessary to get outcomes of this doctrine. Hostile propaganda and global information flows have begun to blur the boundaries between external aggression and domestic opinion formation (Lukin, 2013).

After 2018, the announcement of *Bajwa Doctrine* represented pivotal articulation of how information itself could become strategic advantage. Such rhetoric served multiple purposes. Reinforcing national unity on military terms and countering disinformation, they promoted vigilant narrative in favour of state's ideology. *Bajwa doctrine* also emphasised the importance of cognitive security. However, this communication strategy also raises questions about the thin line between defensive communication and the manufacturing of consent.

The subsequent military model of online communication raised many questions whether the state's narrative of fifth-generation war genuinely served the public interest or it imperceptibly disciplined political discourse. Dominant and powerful institutions often create and circulate messages that reinforce elite

interests while presenting them as objective truths (Khan, 2021). The digital environment further complicates these social and psychological dynamics of ISPR. Social media algorithms prioritise emotionally charged digital content. Because students are among the heaviest users of social media platforms (Pande, 2018), they are always exposed to the influence of both state and non-state actors. Pakistan is no exception. These youths represent demographic spectrum that shape Pakistan's future public sphere. Thus, it is vital to know that how young people in Pakistan internalise and reinterpret messaging within their own socio-political contexts.

One way to characterize fifth-generation war is as a "war of information and perception." Fifth generation war is noteworthy development in which non-state fighters attack nation-states out of pure discontent with no discernible political goals. Everyone agrees that individual acts carried out on their own initiative are crucial component of fifth-generation war. This is the most important aspect of fifth-generation war for our purposes. Fifth-generation war combines cutting-edge technologies like computer science and fully autonomous systems to fight mostly through action, including cyberattacks, social engineering, and (dis)information. Social engineering is the most important attempt to alter specific beliefs and social behaviors on a large scale. These days, fifth-generation war is becoming more common and pervasive, and it might soon be the most deadly for number of nations. I would like to state that fifth-generation war is irreversible, changing our entire perspective on war and posing much bigger threat to countries. It convicts the nations and forces them to come up with new, unprecedented strategies. It changes our viewpoints, forcing us to consider issues other than military prowess.

Problem Statement

This study highlights the dual role of social media as weapon and battleground, which would help policy makers to develop policies that balance national security with democratic norms (Todd & Bloch, 2003). Using quantitatively investigating, it aims to know how university students in Islamabad understand and respond to the ISPR's online messaging on fifth-

generation war. In response to the “*Bajwa Doctrine*”, which framed fifth-generation war as an existential threat, the ISPR expanding its social-media presence to counter perceived adversaries and propaganda has raised the military’s stake (Salma et al., 2023). The study, therefore, seeks to know the statistical relationship between the levels of students’ exposure to military’s social-media content and their agreement with the state’s narrative of the fifth-generation war.

Research Objectives

- To examine how university students in Islamabad perceive and internalize ISPR’s fifth-generation war narratives on social media within the framework of the *Bajwa Doctrine*, using Noam Chomsky’s propaganda model to assess the link between exposure and acceptance of narrative.

Research Questions

- How do university students in Islamabad understand and respond to the ISPR’s messaging on fifth-generation war presented through social media platforms?
- What is the statistical relationship between the level of students’ exposure to ISPR’s social-media content and their agreement with the state’s narrative of fifth-generation war?

Research Hypotheses

- **H₁:** Greater exposure to ISPR’s social-media content is positively associated with higher acceptance of the state’s narrative on fifth-generation war among university students in Islamabad.
- **H₂:** Students with higher levels of critical media literacy demonstrate a weaker relationship between exposure to ISPR messaging and acceptance of the state’s narrative on fifth-generation war.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Media reports and depictions of significant geopolitical developments are usually symptomatic of deeper political, financial, and ideological settings. Finding these ambiances is essential for thorough grasp of international collaborations and safety tactics useful as armed pressure gear. Empirical and policy-oriented

research work focused on specific strategic framework of the *Bajwa Doctrine* (Waheed, 2014). It grounds cognitive security and media frames information campaigns as existential threats. This body of research work collectively emphasises that fifth-generation war in the Pakistani context is not merely theoretical abstraction but strategic communication practice.

The literature on fifth-generation war, information operations, and state-led strategic communication reveals an interdisciplinary conversation (Alam et al., 2025). Inter-Services Public Relations has been transformed from narrow publicity office into comprehensive instrument of strategic communications. It is deploying high-production-value audio-visual material, social media campaigns, and performative diplomacy. Fifth-generation war emphasises greater shift from kinetic engagements to contests over war narratives. Contemporary wars are increasingly seeking to influence public perceptions (Krishnan, 2024). This theoretical interchange highlights the value of blending propaganda-model critiques.

Several studies have adapted Chomsky’s propaganda model insights. These insights non-state actors employ framing, while non-state actors use framing and selective intensification to legitimise security-centric policies. Scholars examining military-media relations and propaganda in Pakistan have strained many contemporary theories (Krishnan, 2022). Comparative research shades the story by showing that military communication is often multi-layered and multifaceted. A sizable section of research studies has documented the social media targeting affordances, which magnify both state messaging and adversarial disinformation (Obiwuru, 2024).

For example, Ullah (2023) surveyed students at Punjab University and found measurable awareness of Fifth-generation war narratives, while Naseer, Sharif, and Akhtar (2024) documented how social media can amplify ethnic rifts through disinformation. Ashraf, Soherwordi, & Javed (2016) applied Herman and Chomsky’s propaganda model to Pakistan’s electronic media, illustrating how ownership, sourcing, and flak shape news agendas.

Related work by Adan, Shabbir, & Ali (2024) analysed how ISPR’s films and dramas cultivate

positive attitudes of university students toward the Pakistani armed forces. In the context of Pakistan, these studies reveal rich conversation about the influence of social media on perceptions of people. Even now, the most hazardous stage of war is fifth-generation war. The fight for sustainable world and the prospects of world peace in the twenty-first century are gravely threatened by this stage. It is time when nations try to destroy one another by cyberattacks instead of armed confrontations. The internet is rife with social engineering, misinformation, and cyberattacks and manipulations. In this era of fifth-generation war, nations are engaged in wars based on "information and perception." During this time, nations are fighting each other in wars centered on commerce, finance, economics, technology, and energy.

Noam Chomsky's propaganda model and related critiques of institutional media capture contemporary theoretical resources. It seeks to counter hostile narratives and maintain institutional legitimacy (Alwan & Muhammad, 2023). Notably, for the focus of this study, university students are highly active on social media platforms (Gunner & Graves, 2025). They may interpret institutional messages through lenses shaped by biased identities. The reviewed literature maps research terrain where the *Bajwa Doctrine* and ISPR's digital campaigns are focused on public opinion and perception. Studies specific to the Pakistani scenario reveal that the ISPR's engagement patterns on Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube are significantly tied to security threats (Santos, 2025).

Network-analytic work and social-cybersecurity investigations further reveal how biased influencer networks interact with official (Whyte et al., 2021). This research gap justifies quantitative survey approach that measures university students' exposure and acceptance of Fifth-generation war narratives (Watson, 2005). University students appraise that ISPR responses function primarily as defensive counter-propaganda. However, it still lacks sufficiently rough quantitative studies that focus on specific populations. University students in

Islamabad are likely to have the most significant influence on future public discourse because of their diversity. There are some serious gaps in empirical research works. Literature examines how digital platforms influence the dynamics of information war. Most of these research studies, however, deal with qualitative approaches. Very rare attention is paid to combining nationwide security doctrine with quantitative audience analysis (Kaptan, 2025).

In his 2021 study, Hamid Khan examines the mechanics of modern war and demonstrates how using information technology and media manipulation is more important in today's wars than traditional military battles. He bemoans the fact that the concept of traditional war is becoming antiquated and describes how, in this new type of battle, media outlets and supercomputers are used to fabricate and spread stories, whether or not they are factual. Research by Akhter (2021) provides a thorough analysis of hybrid war as complex military technique that blends irregular and cybernetic tactics with traditional battlefield tactics.

Although Noam Chomsky's propaganda model is frequently utilized in Western media contexts, it is rarely applied in Pakistan's strategic communication (Lee, 2021). Likewise, although the *Bajwa Doctrine* and the ISPR communication tactics are frequently discussed in policy discussions, they are hardly examined yet. This lack of evidence leaves key questions unanswered about both the effectiveness of these campaigns and their broader democratic implications (Ashraf, 2021).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Noam Chomsky and Edward S. Herman's propaganda model was initially developed to explain structural biases in the United States media (Herman & Chomsky, 2012). This model is built on five major "filters" that influence public opinion and news content: anti-communism, sourcing, ownership, advertising, and flake. The filter of "flak" or negative media responses was later adapted to broader themes of security and fear (Mullen & Klaehn, 2010).

Theoretical framework drawing developed by author

These filters are applied to Pakistani media to help state institutions, particularly the Inter-Services Public Relations. Journalists and social media influencers often rely on official briefings, press releases, and digital content produced by ISPR. Institutions are creating structural incentives to reproduce the state's framing notion of Fifth-generation war (Herman, 1996). By overlaying these filters onto the *Bajwa Doctrine's* conception of fifth-generation war, the analysis emphasises the imperative of cognitive security. The propaganda model provides robust framework for evaluating how ISPR's digital campaigns aim to instil in university students' minds the perceptions of Fifth-generation war. The propaganda model also clarifies how institutional power influences the university students' understanding of security threats. This theoretical framework not only enhances global debates about propaganda, it also provides critical insights into perceptions of fifth-generation war. This research work is contested space where university students' perceptions of dominance are continuously conveyed (Mueller, 2020). The *Bajwa Doctrine* by ISPR sugar-coated this understanding by emphasising information campaigns. Researcher thoroughly examined these concepts and fined

it essential to situate this phenomenon within the broader theoretical frameworks of Noam Chomsky's propaganda model (Cathey, 2009). This model enables researchers to assess whether Pakistan's state-led ISPR narrative serves as defensive strategy against external manipulation or as an internal mechanism for managing domestic wars.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the including research design, sampling strategy, data collection procedures, instrumentation, and data analysis, guided by Noam Chomsky's propaganda model (Nel, 2022). The study employs quantitative research approach to examine how university students in Islamabad understand and respond to the ISPR's messaging on fifth-generation war presented through social media platforms. In addition, what is the statistical relationship between the level of students' exposure to ISPR's social-media content and their agreement with the state's narrative of fifth-generation war? The research design is quantitative survey, chosen for its ability to capture attitudes and perceptions from large population in Islamabad.

The population of interest comprises undergraduate and postgraduate students enrolled in ten leading universities in Islamabad.

These universities include Quaid-i-Azam University, National University of Sciences and Technology (NUST), International Islamic University Islamabad, COMSATS University Islamabad, Bahria University, National Defence University, Air University, FUUAST, NUML, and AIOU Islamabad. A purposive sampling strategy was carefully applied to ensure inclusion of students who are active users of Twitter (X), Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube (Tellis, 1997). The final sample comprises 220 respondents; a stratified purposive approach ensures the sample's heterogeneity. Data were collected carefully through structured online questionnaire. The research instrument shall consist of five sections that measure demographic characteristics, social media usage, frequency of exposure, awareness of fifth-generation war, and levels of acceptance of fifth-generation war narratives (Mullen, 2015). Items are rated on five-point Likert scale, which enabled the application of parametric statistical techniques (Bryman, 2008). Data analysis is conducted using SPSS 27.0. Descriptive statistics of collected data were summarised, including demographic characteristics and social

media habits. All ethical protocols were strictly observed, and no personally identifiable information was collected.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This chapter presents the statistical findings of the research study. The instrument started with description of the demographic profile of the respondents. The selected data were collected from purposive, gender-stratified sample of 220 students from ten leading universities in Islamabad. The first part of the research instrument focuses on demographic characteristics, including age, gender, educational level, and the specific university of each participant. The second section examines social media usage; the time spent online each day, and the nature of the content typically university students are engaged. The third section of the questionnaire examines the frequency of exposure to social media content related to fifth-generation war. The final section assesses levels of acceptance of fifth-generation war narratives. Table 1 below summarises the distribution of respondents from ten universities in Islamabad.

Table 1: Demographic details of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	18-20 years	52	23.6
	21-23 years	92	41.8
	24-26 years	52	23.6
	27 years and above	24	11.0
	Total	220	100
Gender	Male	118	53.64
	Female	102	46.36
	Total	220	100
Educational Level	Undergraduate	134	60.9
	Graduate (Master's)	60	27.3
	Postgraduate (MPhil/PhD)	26	11.8
	Total	220	100
University	Quaid-i-Azam University	36	16.4
	NUST	32	14.5
	Bahria University	24	10.9
	National Defence University	22	10
	IIUI	28	12.7
	COMSATS	26	11.8
	Air University	16	7.3
	NUML	14	6.4
	Federal Urdu University	12	5.5
	Allama Iqbal Open University	10	4.5
Total	220	100	

***No. of responses (n=220)*

Above (table 1) presents the demographic information of university students in Islamabad who participated in the online survey. Empirical finding provides essential background for understanding the research sample's representativeness. Age category shows that the largest age group falls between 21-23 years. This sample includes (41.8 %) of the overall population. From 18-20 and 24-26 years age response category, (23.6 %) respondents are ensuring coverage of both younger undergraduates and students of postgraduate levels. Only (10.9 %) of respondents are in the 27 years and above age response category. Sample of this research study is balanced and managed, with males representing (53.64 %) and females (46.36 %). Demographic contribution of this research study strengthens the validity of gender-based comparisons in media consumption patterns which reflects the gender composition across Islamabad-based ten universities. Undergraduate students form the selected sample is (60.9 %), although graduate students of this research study are (27.3 %),

following (11.8 %) are pursuing MPhil or PhD programs.

It enables the research analysis of how academic maturity and critical thinking skills affect awareness and reactions to ISPR content regarding fifth-generation war. Ten key institutions in the sampling frame are highly represented and valid. Quaid-i-Azam University Islamabad contributes the largest share, at (16.4 %), followed by the National University of Sciences and Technology at (14.5 %). International Islamic University Islamabad at (12.7 %), COMSATS at (11.8 %), and Bahria University at (10.9 %). Furthermore, smaller but expressive groups from National Defence University, Air University, NUML, Federal Urdu University, and Allama Iqbal Open University also ensure their representativeness. Generally, these demographics confirm that the study successfully captures the diverse and representative engagement of Islamabad-based university students. This diversity is crucial for testing whether exposure to ISPR messaging leads to the acceptance or rejection of fifth-generation war narratives.

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics and Social Media Usage of Respondents

Demographic Variable	Category	Mean Daily Social Media Use (hours)	Std. Dev.	Predominant Content Engaged*
Age	18-20 years	3.0	1.0	Entertainment, lifestyle, educational posts
	21-23 years	3.4	1.1	News, political discussions, and entertainment
	24-26 years	3.1	1.0	News, professional/academic content
	27 years and above	2.6	0.9	Professional networking, national news
Gender	Male	3.3	1.1	News, politics, sports, technology
	Female	3.0	1.0	Lifestyle, entertainment, education, and social causes
Educational Level	Undergraduate	3.4	1.1	Entertainment, political debate, trending news
	Graduate (Master's)	3.0	1.0	News, professional development, academic resources
	Postgraduate	2.7	0.9	Research networks, academic forums, and national current affairs

***No. of responses (n=220)*

Table 2 shows the students' engagement in terms of time spent on social media. Students aged 21–23 spend the most time on social media, averaging 3.4 hours per day. This age group typically represents the middle-year undergraduates and graduate students. Age response category 18–20 follows very closely, with social media content usage focused on entertainment and lifestyle content. Gender differences in this response category are slightly modest. Male respondents average 3.3 hours of daily social media engagement. Male respondents are engaged with political news, sports, and information technology content. Although, female respondents use social media for an average of 3.0 hours per day. Female respondents are focusing on news, lifestyle, educational, and socially oriented topics. It influence the probability of encountering Inter-

Services Public Relations (ISPR) messaging. Political and news consumption patterns often increases exposure to ISPR official narratives. The educational level also reveals gradual decline in social media time consumption. Undergraduate students remain the heaviest users. They are spending 3.4 hours per day on entertainment and political debate using social media. At the same time, postgraduate students spent an average of 2.7 hours per day focusing on professional or research-related content. This time configuration suggests that younger students of selected universities are most likely to be exposed to fifth-generation war narratives. The above demographic insights provide critical foundation for testing relationships between age, education, time spent online, and the extent of exposure to ISPR-driven fifth-generation war narratives.

Table 3. Frequency of Exposure to ISPR Content

Platform	Mean Frequency Score	Std. Dev.	High Exposure (%)	Moderate Exposure (%)	Low/No Exposure (%)
Instagram	3.6	1.1	36.4	42.7	20.9
YouTube	3.4	1.3	33.6	44.5	21.9
Facebook	3.2	1.0	31.4	47.3	21.3
Twitter (X)	2.9	0.9	29.5	41.4	29.1

****No. of responses (n=220)**

The results above (Table 3) show that Instagram and YouTube are the most prominent channels for ISPR material, with over one third of respondents reporting high exposure on these social media platforms. Facebook follows these results very closely, while Twitter (X) has the lowest high-exposure rate by university students. Although low or no exposure remains notable in this data collection material, it is especially true on Twitter. This frequency of data helps with critical media literacy and acceptance of fifth-generation war narratives. This table provides detailed overview of the frequency of exposure to fifth-generation war content disseminated by the Inter-Services Public Relations (ISPR), the central focus of this research work. It directly reflects the social media platforms that students use most of the time.

This table is also linked to the study's aim of understanding the digital media dissemination of fifth-generation war messaging. The mean frequency of this research work score indicates

how often respondents encounter the ISPR narrative about the fifth-generation war on selected social media platforms. Likert-type scale is used for meaning score ranging from low to high exposure, 1-5. Use of Instagram is high which leads with highest mean score of 3.6, followed by YouTube score (3.4). This is highlighting the role of video content of ISPR-produced video clips and documentaries. It is used in shaping students' perceptions of national security in the broader context of fifth-generation war narrative. Moreover, Facebook mean score is (3.2), Twitter (X) shows the lowest mean score at (2.9). The SD values provide additional insight where the Instagram and Facebook have relatively low standard deviations, such as (1.1 and 1.0). Use of YouTube shows slightly higher variability (1.3). Twitter have lower mean and smaller standard deviation (0.9) reflect a narrower range of social media engagement among students. YouTube follows with (33.6 %), Facebook with (31.4 %),

and Twitter with (29.5 %), ranging from (41.4 %) on Twitter to (47.3 %) on Facebook. Low exposure is highest on Twitter at (29.1 %),

indicating that nearly third of students either avoid or rarely interact with ISPR narratives on selected social media platforms.

Table 4. Awareness of Fifth-Generation War among Students

Variable	Mean Score	Std. Dev	High Awareness (%)	Moderate Awareness (%)	Low/No Awareness (%)
Familiarity with the term Fifth Generation War	3.6	0.9	38.2	42.7	19.1
Understanding of definition of Fifth Generation War	3.4	0.8	34.5	45.0	20.5
Perceived relevance of Fifth Generation War with national security	3.7	0.7	40.0	44.1	15.9

****No. of responses (n=220)**

This table 4 indicates that substantial proportion of university students have moderate to high awareness about social media usage and platforms, particularly regarding the relevance of fifth-generation war. The first variable has a mean score of 3.6 with a standard deviation of 0.9, indicating that most students have a high familiarity with the concept of fifth-generation war. The distribution shows that (38.2 %) of students are highly familiar with this concept. Although (42.7 %) have moderate familiarity, and (19.1 %) have lower level of awareness. This suggests that while nearly two-thirds of the sample recognise the term. The second variable, when understood, has slightly lower mean of 3.4

and a standard deviation of 0.8. (34.5 %) The majority of respondents have moderate awareness (45 %), and low or no understanding (20.5 %). This indicates that while students are generally aware of the term fifth generation war. The third variable, “Perceived relevance to national security”, also has the highest mean score of 3.7 and the lowest standard deviation of 0.7, suggesting strong and relatively uniform perception that fifth-generation war is essential for Pakistan’s security. Here, (40 %) of students report high relevance, (44.1 %) moderate relevance, and (15.9 %) low or no relevance.

Table 5. Acceptance of Fifth-Generation War Narratives among Students

Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	High Acceptance (%)	Moderate Acceptance (%)	Low/No Acceptance (%)
Pakistan is under constant fifth-generation attack	3.89	0.84	42.3	38.2	19.5
Social media is a battlefield for hostile states through Fifth Generation War	4.02	0.78	44.1	39.5	16.4
ISPR campaigns help protect national security against Fifth Generation War	3.75	0.81	39.1	42.3	18.6
Criticising ISPR narratives weakens the country	2.42	0.92	32.7	41.4	25.9

Overall Acceptance Index	3.77	0.69	39.5	41.8	18.7
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****No. of responses (n=220)**

The table 5 shows that respondents have moderate to high acceptance of ISPR narratives, particularly regarding the perception of social media as fifth-generation war. This table provides a detailed overview of students' levels of acceptance of fifth-generation war narratives. There are five statements that respondents are asked to evaluate. The statement "Social media is a battlefield for hostile states" received the highest mean score of 4.02 with standard deviation of 0.78, indicating strong agreement among students. High acceptance was reported by (44.1 %) of respondents, moderate by (39.5 %), and only (16.4 %) reported low or no acceptance. The second statement, "Pakistan is under constant fifth-generation attack", has a greater mean score of 3.89 and a standard deviation of 0.84. High acceptance is recorded at (42.3 %), moderate at (38.2 %), and low or no

acceptance at (19.5 %). For the third statement, "ISPR campaigns help protect national security," the mean is 3.75 with a standard deviation of 0.81. Here, (39.1 %) of respondents reported high acceptance, while (42.3 %) reported moderate acceptance. The fourth statement, "Criticising ISPR narratives weakens the country", received the lowest mean score of 2.42 with a standard deviation of 0.92. Only (32.7 %) of students showed high acceptance, (41.4 %) showed moderate acceptance, and (25.9 %) showed low or no acceptance. The Overall Acceptance Index combines these items into a composite measure, with a mean of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 0.69. High acceptance is observed in (39.5 %) of students, moderate acceptance in (41.8 %), and low or no acceptance in (18.7 %).

Table 6. Correlation between ISPR Exposure and Acceptance of Fifth-Generation War Narrative

Variables	1	2	Mean (M)	Std. Dev. (SD)
ISPR Social-Media Exposure regarding Fifth Generation War	—	.62**	3.36	0.92
Acceptance of fifth generation War Narrative	.62**	—	3.77	0.69

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation. Fifth generation= Fifth-Generation. ***No. of responses (n=220)**

The above table 6 reveals the results of the Correlation between ISPR Exposure and Acceptance of the Fifth-Generation War Narrative (N = 220). The first variable, ISPR Social-Media Exposure, represents the frequency and intensity with which students encounter content produced by the Inter-Services Public Relations (ISPR) across various social media platforms. The standard deviation of 0.92 reflects a moderate level of variation. Some

students encounter ISPR messaging daily or multiple times a day, while others have less consistent exposure. The mean score of 3.77 shows that the average respondent moderately endorses the official narrative of ISPR. The standard deviation of 0.69 indicates that there is slightly less variation in acceptance compared to exposure. The Pearson correlation coefficient between the two variables is (0.62), which is statistically significant at the 0.01 level.

Table 7. Independent-Samples t-Test Comparing High vs. Low ISPR Exposure on Acceptance of Fifth Generation War Narrative

Exposure Group	N***	Mean Acceptance	Std. Dev.	t	df	p-value
High ISPR Exposure related to Fifth Generation War	78	4.12	0.58	8.34	218	<0.001

Low/Moderate Exposure related to Fifth Generation War 142 3.52 0.63

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation. Fifth Generation= Fifth-Generation. ***No. of responses (n=220)**

Table 7 presents the results of an independent-samples t-test comparing the acceptance of fifth-generation war narratives among university students of Islamabad. It provides unconditional test of the research hypothesis H_1 . The High ISPR Exposure group exhibits mean acceptance score of (4.12) with standard deviation of (0.58). The Low Exposure group with mean acceptance

of (3.52) and a standard deviation of (0.63). The t-value of 8.34 with 218 degrees of freedom and a p-value < 0.001 indicates that the difference in mean acceptance between the two groups is statistically significant. Results also confirm that students with higher exposure to ISPR content have significantly greater acceptance of the fifth-generation war narrative.

Table 8. Correlation between ISPR Exposure and Acceptance of Fifth Generation War Narrative by Critical Media Literacy Level

Critical Media Literacy Group	N	Mean Acceptance	Std. Dev.	Pearson r (Exposure ↔ Acceptance)
High Media Literacy	102	3.58	0.64	0.41**
Low/Moderate Media Literacy	118	3.92	0.66	0.68**

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

Table 8 presents the moderating role of critical media literacy in the relationship between exposures to ISPR social media content. This is also second hypothesis of my research study. High media literacy group has mean acceptance score of (3.58) with standard deviation of (0.64). The Pearson correlation between variables is (0.41). Statistically significant at the 0.01 level which is weaker than for students with lower media literacy. The low media literacy group exhibits a higher mean acceptance score of (3.92) and a slightly larger standard deviation of (0.66). The correlation between exposure and acceptance in this group is (0.68), also significant at the 0.01 level.

DISCUSSION

The present study explored the relationship between university students’ social media exposure to ISPR fifth-generation war narrative. 220 students from ten major universities in Islamabad were systematically accessed to get relevant data. Researcher used demographic analysis, social media usage, frequency of exposure, awareness of fifth-generation war, and acceptance of ISPR narratives. Demographic characteristics of selected sample revealed that the majority of respondents were aged between

21–23 years (41.8 %), with gender distribution (53.6 % male and 46.4 %). In education category majority of respondents are under graduate (60.9 %). Remaining sample is consist of graduate or postgraduate level which reflected diverse student population in terms of there academic background.

Use of social media indicated that Instagram and YouTube were the most popular platforms, with mean daily usage of (2.8) and (2.5) hours, respectively. (36.4 %) of students reported high exposure on Instagram, (33.6 %) on YouTube, and lower levels on Facebook and Twitter for ISPR contents polarization. Most students recognise the strategic importance of the concept, it indicates that ISPR messaging may effectively raise awareness of fifth-generation war threats without necessarily promoting detailed comprehension. Acceptance of ISPR campaigns’ protective role was slightly lower (M = 3.75), while agreement that criticising ISPR weakens the country was more moderate (M = 2.42). Hypothesis testing confirmed that higher exposure to ISPR content is strongly associated with greater acceptance of the narrative (r = 0.62, p < 0.01). The independent-samples t-test further validates that those with high exposure reported significantly higher acceptance scores

($M = 4.12$) than those with low or moderate exposure ($M = 3.52$, $t(218) = 8.34$, $p < 0.001$). Students with higher critical media literacy displayed weaker correlation between exposure and acceptance ($r = 0.41$) compared to their peers with low to medium literacy ($r = 0.68$). Even among high-exposure students, those with advanced media literacy reported lower acceptance ($M = 3.84$) than those with low literacy ($M = 4.32$).

SUMMARY

This study examined how ISPR disseminates fifth-generation war narratives via intensive use of social media and how university students in Islamabad perceive and accept these narratives. The findings of this research work emphasise the need for media literacy in the context of state-driven narratives. The study establishes that Instagram and YouTube are the most frequently used platforms, serving as key channels for exposure to official ISPR messaging, where ISPR has 529k followers on Instagram and has approximately 5.2 million likes on Facebook. The official ISPR YouTube channel, "@ISPR," has over 6.39 million subscribers as of late 2025 and serves as the primary source for content from Pakistan's Armed Forces. Students demonstrated moderate to high awareness of fifth-generation war, though comprehension of its full definition was less common.

Acceptance of the official narrative was found strong, particularly regarding the portrayal of social media under constant fifth-generation war. Statistical analysis confirmed that greater exposure to ISPR content is positively associated with higher acceptance of these narratives. Persuasive impact of repeated messaging by ISPR significantly affect critical media literacy of university students thoroughly. Students with higher media literacy showed weaker correlation between exposure and acceptance of the ISPR fifth-generation war narrative. Overall, the study demonstrates that social media serves as significant arena for fifth-generation war.

The term "fifth-generation war" has been widely used in contemporary military discourse, it is still complex and ambiguous concept. Researchers have made an effort to clarify several aspects of fifth-generation war. Experts claim that five variables are usually involved in fifth-generation warfare: economic structures, social

dynamics, information diffusion, physical barriers, and cognitive considerations. Adversaries employ fifth-generation war tactics to combat states in order to accomplish their goals by organizing non-state actors within nation. State actors in the nation are fiercely competing with one another for authority and legitimacy. Cultural superiority is delicate topic, even though economic marginalization can play major role in fifth-generation war. In fifth-generation war, multiple parties within state compete with one another for power.

It is important to remember that any such move would have far-reaching effects. Nuclear clouds will loom over the entire area as long as India and Pakistan are at war because there is no assurance that such limited offensives will always remain limited. In order to defend themselves, Pakistan's ruling class would need to seriously reconsider its national security strategy in the event of fifth-generation war strike on both society and the state. Adopting thorough plan to counter fifth-generation war would be essential to preventing a national disaster.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The findings of this study highlights the urgent need for coordinated national security response to counter social media propaganda. Following policy recommendations are framed to implement in broader national interest.

- State should prioritize the development of comprehensive digital information security framework. PEMRA, NCCIA, FIA and PTA joint venture, must be strengthened with updated mandates to monitor coordinated (dis)information campaigns. Study demonstrates that university students remain vulnerable to emotionally framed propaganda and conspiracy theories.
- Higher education policy should broadly incorporate structured media literacy and critical thinking modules into university curriculum focusing national security and interest.
- Faculty development programs must also be introduced to better equip instructors with contemporary knowledge of fifth-generation war tactics, enabling classrooms to function as counter narrative engagement rather than passive

consumption. HEC should institutionalize courses focusing on digital verification skills and propaganda analysis of information war.

- State institutions, including PEMRA, ISPR and relevant civil ministries, need to adopt data-driven communication strategies. This includes ethical use of influencers, transparent messaging, and consistent fact-based engagement to prevent (dis)information vacuums that are often exploited by non-state actors.
- Last but not least, national security policy must acknowledge perception management as central component of contemporary war narrative. Inter-agency coordination between security institutions, academia, and civil society should be dignified through research partnerships and information-sharing mechanisms.

LIMITATIONS AND DELIMITATIONS

The present study is subject to several limitations

- This research is geographically narrowed to university students in Islamabad, which limits the generalizability of the results.
- Students in the federal capital are more likely to have higher digital and financial exposure and better access to information war narratives, therefore the perceptions and experiences captured in this study may not fully reflect the diversity of social media usage patterns.
- Second, the study relies heavily on self-reported data collected through survey instruments, respondents' interpretations of abstract concepts such as propaganda, disinformation, and perception manipulation may vary.
- Third, the cross-sectional design of the research captures perceptions and attitudes at a single point in time, limiting the ability to assess changes in awareness, and media behaviour over extended periods.
- The study focuses primarily on students' perceptions and interpretations of fifth-generation war narratives rather than conducting comprehensive content and network analysis of social media platforms.
- Finally, this study is theoretically grounded in propaganda model, it does not

incorporate psychological and mythological measures that could offer deeper insights into emotional susceptibility.

FUTURE RESEARCH STUDIES

- This research should bridge gap between use of social media and fifth-generation war narrative. So, future research should expand the scope limitation and authenticity of research inquiry beyond the geographical and demographic boundaries to enhance the generalizability of current research findings.
- A comparative studies involving university students from other provinces, is also suggested to explore Longitudinal research designs are essential to capture the evolving nature of social media propaganda, (dis)information and its cumulative effects on perception manipulation of university students of Pakistan.
- Additional research should also incorporate advanced theoretical and methodological approaches, including computational and social science techniques. Content analysis using artificial intelligence, digital media and social network analysis, can empirically map the spread, intensity, and sources of fifth-generation war narratives
- There is also need for experimental and psychological studies that examine the cognitive and emotional mechanisms underlying perception manipulation.

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